

EFFECT OF GRAIN SIZE OF β - Si_3N_4 AND GLASSY PHASE ON STRENGTH AND FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF IN-SITU TOUGHENED Si_3N_4

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ABSTRACT

An in-situ toughened Si_3N_4 ceramic is obtained by hot-pressing, its flexural strength and fracture toughness are 960MPa, $12.74\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$ at room temperature and 720MPa, $23.94\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$ at 1350°C , respectively. The relation between grain size of β - Si_3N_4 and mechanical properties is investigated. The glassy phase containing Y and La plays an important role in increasing high temperature mechanical properties because of its high viscosity and softening temperature. Crack deflection, crack branching and pullout of rodlike β - Si_3N_4 crystals are observed in this material by SEM, and the toughening mechanisms are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Silicon nitride ceramics are recognized for their excellent mechanical and physical properties, including good wear resistance, low coefficient of thermal expansion, good thermal shock resistance, high creep resistance, and good oxidation resistance, but its failure is generally associated with brittleness and flaws. Whisker reinforcement is the alternative way to increase the fracture toughness of ceramics matrix^[1]. This technique, however, does not provide significant toughening in the case of silicon nitride ceramic, and there are difficulties to be solved such as whisker dispersion, densification, and whisker stability.

In-situ toughening is a novel process with which the fracture toughness is increased by reasonable control of the microstructure, especially the grains growth of rodlike β - Si_3N_4 and the glassy phase at the grain boundary, without adding any reinforcing agent. It is known that the presence of β -silicon nitride with a high aspect ratio can increase the fracture toughness of Si_3N_4 ceramics, as reported by Lange^[2]. Faber et al.^[3] studied crack deflection toughening process with elongated grains in Si_3N_4 matrix theoretically, Wotting et al.^[4] examined the relation between mechanical properties of sintered Si_3N_4 . The results show elongated β - Si_3N_4 grain increase the fracture toughness. Tani et al.^[5] prepared high toughness Si_3N_4 with fiber-like structure by adding

Al_2O_3 and 5wt% rare earth oxide. Obviously Si_3N_4 consisting of elongated in-situ grown $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grains has great advantage based on its composite microstructure. The use of rare earth oxide is associated with increasing of softening temperature and viscosity of glassy phase at grain boundary, so Si_3N_4 ceramics have an excellent properties at elevated temperature^[6]. Therefore hot-pressed Si_3N_4 with Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 as sintering aids is one of the most promising materials as high toughness ceramics.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Silicon nitride powder ($\alpha\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4 > 95\%$, 1.5wt%O, Shanghai institute of materials) and an equimolar ratio of Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 (99.95% pure, Yuelong Chemical Co., Shanghai, China) were ball-milled in ethanol for 24h. Slurries were then dried at $\sim 85^\circ\text{C}$ on a hot plate with magnetic stirring to prevent any sedimentation of weigher particles. Hot-pressing is accomplished in BN-coated graphite dies at $1750^\circ \sim 1800^\circ\text{C}$, 30MPa, for 30~120 minutes in a nitrogen atmosphere with a pressure of 0.1MPa.

Specimens for bending strength tests and fracture toughness tests were ground to $3\text{mm} \times 4\text{mm} \times 36\text{mm}$ and $5\text{mm} \times 2.5\text{mm} \times 26\text{mm}$ of which the single edge notched depth is 2.5mm using an 800-grit diamond wheel. The flexural strength were tested with 5 specimens for each condition using a three-point bending method with a 30mm span at a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/s. Fracture toughness was measured using Single-Edge Precracked Beam(SEPB) method^[7] with 20mm span at a crosshead speed of 0.05m/s. Phases in the ceramics were determined by XRD. Sintered sample were polished and etched for microstructure observation using scanning electron microscopy. Etching was done by immersing the specimens into molten mixed alkali hydroxides (with a composition of $\text{LiOH}:\text{NaOH}:\text{KOH} = 1:2:2$) in a pure Al_2O_3 crucible at about 450°C for 60 to 80s. The surface was then washed and disintegrated in water with an ultrasonic vibrator. The loose grains collected at the bottom of a beaker were used for grain size measurement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure and Grain Size of $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$

XRD analysis shows that all the $\alpha\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ were transformed into $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ crystals after sintering for 60min at temperatures ranging from 1750° to 1800°C , a typical microstructure photograph consisting of rodlike $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ crystals and glassy phase is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Microstructure photograph of Si_3N_4 . Sample was sintered at 1800°C for 60min, etching by mixed alkali hydroxides for 80s.

Figure 2 illustrates the aspect ratio distribution of three specimens sintered at 1800 °C for 30min, 60min, and 120min, respectively. The grain size of these disintegrated grains can be determined without any stereological consideration. At least 500 grains were measured for each specimen to get essential consistent results.

Fig. 2. Aspect ratio distribution of β -Si₃N₄ at 1800°C for sintering time of ●30min ■60min ▲120min.

As illustrated in Fig.2, the aspect ratio (AR) of the β -Si₃N₄ follows a normal distribution, and the average AR for each specimen is about 2, 7.5 and 10, respectively. With increasing sintering time, the β -Si₃N₄ grains grow and the large grain number per unit volume increases, but, the growth in the axial direction is faster than that of the radial direction. Thirty minutes of sintering time results in relatively small β -Si₃N₄ grains, while, 60min of sintering time makes large β -Si₃N₄ grains of 1~5 μm in diameter and 10~40 μm in length.

Grain Size of β -Si₃N₄ and K_{IC} , σ_f Relation Analysis

It is reported^[8] that fracture toughness (K_{IC}) increases with increasing aspect ratio (AR) of grains. Figure 3 illustrates the relation between K_{IC} and AR, Diameter of β -Si₃N₄. The K_{IC} goes up quickly when AR of β -Si₃N₄ is increased below 5. Further increase of AR results in slower increase of K_{IC} , as the diameter has a significant effect. If the diameter of the rodlike β -Si₃N₄ is too small to make crack deflection, the small rodlike β -Si₃N₄ would break to decrease the fracture toughness. Also the critical diameter of grains is expected to be around 1 μm.

Fig.3. Plots of K_{IC} and AR, Diameter

In general, the smaller the grain size is, the larger the intergranular surface area has and the higher the strength of specimens is. Sintering time has an important effect on grains size of β - Si_3N_4 , and results in flexural strength changing, it is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Flexural strength of sintered Si_3N_4 in different sintering time

Sintering time (min)	Average AR of β - Si_3N_4	Flexural strength (MPa)
30	2	640
60	7.5	960
120	10	860

Increases of the AR result in a linear increase in strength, whereas increases in the grain size at a comparable grain morphology reduce the strength, the relation between strength and grain size corresponds to the equation

$$\sigma_f = (\text{Constant}) \text{AR} / \sqrt{D} \quad (1)$$

where σ_f is the strength, AR the aspect ratio, and D the grain diameter. As sintering time increases, AR and diameter of β - Si_3N_4 increase to promote the grain size unusual growth, therefore, the flexural strength has a slightly decrease.

Influence of Glassy Phase on High Temperature Fracture Toughness and Flexural strength

Glassy phase at grain boundary with high softening temperature has an effect of improving high temperature mechanical properties of Si_3N_4 ceramics. For in-situ toughened Si_3N_4 with Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 as additives, Oxynitride glass containing Y and La is formed at grain boundary, this kind of glass has a high softening temperature and high viscosity because of its high nitrogen-content^[9]. A eutectic-type phase diagram was reported for Y_2O_3 - La_2O_3 and the minimum liquid formation temperature is about 1550°C at 20 Y_2O_3 · 80 La_2O_3 (mol%)^[10]. In Si_3N_4 - Y_2O_3 - La_2O_3 system, the liquid formation is lower than 1550°C because of the impurities such as SiO_2 on surface of Si_3N_4 powder. The more the additives are, the more the glassy phase is. The glassy phase has significant influences on high temperature mechanical properties. Figure 4. shows that a high flexural strength can retain from room temperature to 1350°C. At 1400°C, the flexural strength only decreases by 25%. However, the fracture toughness increases with the temperature going up because of the softened glassy phase playing a part in curing pores and blunting cracks. At 1350°C, the fracture toughness reaches 23.94 $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$, better than that of the best yet reported whisker-reinforced Si_3N_4 composites up to now.

Toughening Mechanisms

In self-reinforced Si_3N_4 fabricated using α - Si_3N_4 powder fracture toughness has been reported to increase proportionally to the square root of the diameter of the large grains, indicating that the bridging of large grains contributes to toughening^[11,12]. In these experiments, the AR and critical grain diameter to deflect and branch the propagating crack is identified by microstructure analysis. Figure 5 shows the crack deflection in an

Fig.4 Mechanical properties of in-situ toughened Si₃N₄ vs temperature

Fig. 5. Photograph of crack deflection in rodlike β -Si₃N₄ grains

in-situ toughened Si₃N₄ with rodlike β -Si₃N₄ grains. It is reported that the fracture toughness can be expressed as^[13]

$$K_{IC} = 10.8L / L_0 - 4.3 \quad (2)$$

where L is the length of the crack running path, and L₀ the distance between crack origin and end. According to the theory of crack deflection, toughening effect depends on the deflection angle. In this materials, the crack deflects when it propagates in front of elongated β -Si₃N₄ grain. Since the elongated rodlike β -Si₃N₄ grains disperse randomly in all directions, the fracture toughness can be improved further because of a large length of crack running-path. In the present work, high fracture toughness is obtained when AR is about 5~ 10 and grain diameter larger than 1 μ m.

In addition, the phenomena of crack branching and pullout of rodlike β -Si₃N₄ are obviously observed when the β -Si₃N₄ grain size is larger enough (length in 30~ 50 μ m, Diameter in 1~ 2 μ m). This is easily achieved by controlling the rodlike β -Si₃N₄ crystal growth.

CONCLUSIONS

In-situ toughening is an effective approach to increase the fracture toughness of Si_3N_4 . The in-situ toughened Si_3N_4 ceramics added with Y_2O_3 and La_2O_3 have excellent mechanical properties, its flexural strength and fracture toughness are 960 MPa, 12.74 $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$ at room temperature and 720MPa, 23.94 $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$ at 1350°C , respectively.

The grain size of β - Si_3N_4 has significant effect on flexural strength and fracture toughness. When the AR is about 5~ 10 and diameter larger than $1\mu\text{m}$, the fracture toughness has a considerable increase. However, the unusual growth of large grains decreases slightly the flexural strength. Oxynitride glassy phase containing Y and La has high softening temperature and high viscosity, and can increase high temperature strength and fracture toughness.

Crack deflection is one of the main toughening mechanism. In addition, crack branching and pullout of rodlike β - Si_3N_4 crystals also show an apparent tendency to contribute to toughening.

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